

Urban Relief

Mannheim Pilot Report

D4.8

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Short description	D4.8 presents two citizen-driven Urban ReLeaf campaigns in Mannheim that address urban heat stress and improve the usability of public spaces. Through a mobile app documenting urban trees and a survey-based study of thermal comfort in central squares, citizens contribute data that supports climate-adaptive, inclusive urban planning and strengthens urban resilience.
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Acronyms

BUGA	Bundesgartenschau (Federal Garden Show)
GmbH	Gesellschaft mit beschränkter Haftung (company with limited liability)
HAP	Heat Action Plan
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans
TRH	Temperature and Relative Humidity

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Executive Summary

Mannheim, one of Germany's hottest cities, faces significant challenges in its densely built-up city centre, where high summer temperatures reduce comfort and usability of public spaces. Within *Urban ReLeaf*, two citizen-driven campaigns have been implemented to enhance urban green infrastructure and improve thermal comfort for residents, with a particular focus on vulnerable groups.

The **Urban Trees Campaign** enables citizens to document and update information on urban trees using the mobile app "Urban ReLeaf – Mannheim's Trees". This activity expands the municipal tree registry, generates shared knowledge about Mannheim's urban greenery, and supports informed decision-making for urban planning and climate adaptation. The app was released in July 2024 and now has more than 140 users.

The **Greenspace Perceptions Campaign - "Cool bleiben auf Mannheims Plätzen"** (July-August 2025) investigates how residents experience central public squares – Alter Meßplatz, Friedrichsplatz, Marktplatz, Paradeplatz, and Schillerplatz – during hot days. The campaign focuses on thermal comfort and the quality of stay, providing insights into how public spaces can be adapted to reduce heat stress and offer shade, comfort, and recreational opportunities. Approximately 280 participants were asked about their experiences of heat and the design of public spaces to identify conditions that support comfort and usability during hot days. Data collected will inform strategies for future-proof urban design and enhance the well-being of all city inhabitants.

Through active citizen participation in data collection and project design, Mannheim is co-developing actionable knowledge for climate adaptation, strengthening urban resilience, and creating more liveable and inclusive public spaces.

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Background on the Urban ReLeaf Project and City Pilots

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. The project addresses the challenges of increasing environmental stresses in urban areas, accentuated inequalities in access to high-quality greenspace, lack of suitable data for planning and decision making as well as inclusion in public participation in science and research.

The main objectives of Urban ReLeaf are to:

- Understand current data ecosystem and urban greening and participation policies in six pilot cities and co-develop opportunities for citizen science and citizen participation to complement existing practices.
- Mobilise and empower local communities in issues of public interest surrounding urban green infrastructure and environmental stewardship.
- Support the long-term inclusion of active and passive data from citizens within official data streams for urban monitoring, planning and innovation in public policy.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and training across relevant actors beyond the six pilot cities by establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.
- Offer flexible and innovative ways of governance that can underpin inclusive green urban planning in support of the European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In pursuit of urban climate resilience, six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities co-create participatory, and data-driven innovations to democratise urban greenspace monitoring and the wider policy making process.

The City of Mannheim is one of these six pilot cities and conducted two campaigns during the project period, the details of which are presented below.

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1 Urban Trees Campaign

The Mannheim Urban Trees Campaign is a citizen science initiative designed to expand and update the city's tree database. Leveraging the Urban ReLeaf – Mannheim's Trees mobile app, residents are encouraged to document trees in their neighbourhoods, recording attributes such as species, location, height, and stem circumference. This collaborative effort aims to enhance the city's tree data while fostering public awareness of the importance of urban greenery for climate resilience, heat protection, and quality of life. Moreover, the tree registry intends to help municipal departments optimise management processes and identify potential locations for future tree planting efforts.

The campaign combines digital participation through the mobile app with on-the-ground engagement at public events and in local neighbourhoods. Activities include thematic micro-campaigns, guided tree-mapping walks, and presence at community fairs. The focus is on areas with particularly high heat stress, but also on neighbourhoods such as Feudenheim, where there is active civic engagement in terms of tree-related requests to the city council.

Running throughout 2024 and 2025, the campaign follows a dynamic timeline aligned with Mannheim's public events calendar. Key highlights include the New Year's Receptions, participation in the Greening Fairs, and a district walk that directly involve residents in data collection. Through this approach, the Mannheim Urban Trees Campaign seeks to engage citizens citywide, improve the quality and completeness of urban tree data, tree preservation, and strengthen community connections to green infrastructure – contributing to Urban ReLeaf's mission of inclusive, data-driven urban greening.

1.1 Context and Objectives

Mannheim faces growing environmental challenges from climate change, particularly extreme summer heat. As one of the hottest cities in Germany, prolonged heatwaves affect the entire population, with vulnerable groups at especially high risk. With average temperatures expected to rise by about 2°C by 2050 and 3.0-4.8°C by 2100, alongside an increased risk of extreme weather events, adaptation to climate change is urgently needed. Trees play a central role in the city's climate adaptation strategies.

This local challenge connects directly to broader regional, national, and EU priorities. At the EU level, the campaign aligns with the European Green Deal and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, which call for enhanced urban green infrastructure, citizen engagement, and nature-based solutions to climate adaptation. Nationally and regionally, the initiative supports Germany's climate adaptation strategies and Baden-Württemberg's commitments to sustainable urban development.

Mannheim also has municipal concepts, strategies and guiding principles that form a valuable framework for the Urban Trees Campaign and reflect the project goals for climate action, urban resilience, and participatory governance. The "[Adaptation to climate change in Mannheim](#)" concept was developed in a broad-based participatory process with internal city administration stakeholders as well as Mannheim's citizens and companies and was adopted by the municipal council in April 2019. On November 17, 2022, the Mannheim City Council adopted the [Climate Protection Action Plan 2030](#) (SECAP) as the central strategy for achieving climate neutrality in Mannheim. It includes targets and areas of action for the administration and for the entire urban community, including businesses and citizens. The plan also covers the field of blue-green infrastructure in the context of nature-based climate protection. In addition, the city council is currently in the process of developing a biodiversity strategy. By developing a new biodiversity strategy, the city aims to create a basis for implementing concrete measures

to protect nature and preserve ecosystems. The aim is to motivate all population groups in Mannheim to actively participate in this process. Citizen participation plays an important role in Mannheim, helping to shape the city together with its residents and strengthen democracy. Involving citizens is firmly anchored in the [Mannheim 2030 mission statement](#).

Expanding and preserving urban greenery, especially through tree planting and maintenance, is a proven and necessary measure to mitigate heat stress, improve air quality, enhance biodiversity, and create more livable public spaces. For this reason, the 1,000 Trees Program was launched in Mannheim. The program aims to replant trees in existing planting areas and create new tree locations in urban areas. Since 2020, the city of Mannheim has been planting more trees every year. Until 2019, the number was up to 300 per year, but since the winter half-year 2024/2025, it has now reached 1,000 for the first time.

Mannheim maintains a tree registry that records the existing tree stock as well as other georeferenced information on tree species, physical attributes, and locations in public spaces. Despite existing municipal efforts, the city's current tree registry contains data gaps and outdated information regarding tree condition, height, crown diameter, and site characteristics. Limited public access to this data also restricts wider engagement and informed decision-making.

The overarching objectives of the Mannheim Urban Trees Campaign are to:

- Expand and improve the city's urban tree data by engaging citizens in registering and updating information on existing trees throughout Mannheim.
- Increase public awareness and engagement in urban greening, tree preservation, and climate adaptation, fostering a sense of shared ownership and stewardship over the city's green infrastructure.
- Enable data-driven decision-making by providing municipal departments with tree data, supporting strategic planning for maintenance, planting, and climate resilience measures.

By addressing these objectives, the campaign contributes to creating a more inclusive, sustainable, and climate-resilient Mannheim while demonstrating a replicable model for other European cities.

1.2 Design and Implementation

The Urban Trees Campaign was conceived as a participatory initiative within the Urban ReLeaf project to expand and update the city's official tree database, while at the same time fostering public awareness of urban greening as a climate protection and adaptation strategy. At its core, the campaign invited residents to become active contributors by using the Urban ReLeaf – Mannheim's Trees mobile app to record information on trees in their surroundings, including location, species, height, and stem circumference.

Campaign development and delivery relied on a collaborative network of partners. The City of Mannheim's Greening Department and Urban Planning Department provided technical oversight and prepared data integration into the municipal registry. The Climate Protection Agency supported the campaign by aligning campaign activities with existing environmental activities. Community organisations, clubs, and neighbourhood associations played an equally vital role, acting as multipliers who mobilised residents and provided local insights. This

combination of technical expertise and community connection shaped both the campaign's reach and its credibility.

The aim was to build on existing events or groups in order to make access as easy as possible. Therefore, the campaign calendar was strategically aligned with high-visibility events and optimal seasonal conditions for tree observation. The approach was generally wide-ranging. However, three target audiences were given particular focus: vulnerable individuals, in particular those vulnerable to heat in neighbourhoods with high heat stress, individuals with an existing interest or even expertise in the field of (urban) greening, and generally active population groups who are engaged in community work.

The communication consistently centred on three key messages:

- Mapping trees is a direct way to contribute to climate adaptation,
- Urban greenery plays a vital role in cooling the city and enhancing quality of life, and
- Participation from all residents - regardless of age, background, or technical expertise - is valuable in expanding the urban tree registry.

In July 2023 a project page on the city of Mannheim's website was established to provide information on the implementation of Urban ReLeaf. The project was included in the city's existing online participation portal into the project list in March 2024, and a dedicated theme room was created in June 2024 to support ongoing communication and citizen involvement in the city's climate and urban resilience initiatives, targeting the broader public. This can be seen as preparation for the public launch of the first campaign in Mannheim at the beginning of summer 2024.

The first Mannheim Greening Fair, *Blumme & Bääm*, held on June 8, 2024, provided an ideal launch for the Urban Trees Campaign. The Kapuzinerplanken in the city centre were transformed into a green oasis for the day, attracting an audience interested in urban greening. During the event, the Urban ReLeaf app was presented to the public and press by Mannheim's First Mayor, Ms. Prof. Dr. Pretzell (Figure 1). The event was promoted in Mannheim's trams, on social media, and in the official city journal to draw attention both to the Greening Fair and to the launch of the campaign.

Figure 1. Promotion at greening fair Blumme und Bääm 2024 (Julian Beekmann).

The Urban Trees Campaign launch event was followed by a hybrid approach of citywide promotion and targeted district-level outreach. Activities ranged from a guided tree walk and participation in smaller events (e.g. Vogelstang neighbourhood festival or Climate Hero-Event) to information booths at major public events such as the New Year's Reception (with more than 8.000 visitors), Heat Action Day or the Greening Fair 2025 (Figure 2). Outreach in high-

footfall events helped engage people who might not actively seek out citizen science activities and lead to participation in communities that might otherwise remain underrepresented. Digital channels, including social media, the Urban ReLeaf project page and the city's official journal, complemented in-person activities by sharing event details, app updates, and participant success stories.

Figure 2. Booth at greening fair Blumme und Bäum 2025 (Julian Beekmann).

Repeated appearances at events and in the same media proved to be a sensible strategy for gaining trust and visibility. Urban ReLeaf and the tree campaign were first introduced at the 2024 New Year's reception (Figure 3 and Figure 4), and the following year, the app was presented at the same event and could be tested directly on site. The same applies to the greening fair and articles in the Max2, a supplement to the Mannheim daily newspaper (Mannheimer Morgen) and the annual report of the Mannheim climate protection agency. This created opportunities for recognition and thus made it easier to establish a personal connection to the project.

Figure 3. Promotion at New Year's Reception (Andreas Henn).

On-site assistance and live demonstrations supported residents unfamiliar with the app which lowered the barrier for first-time contributors.

Figure 4. Table at New Year's Reception (Andreas Henn).

In the majority of the activities and publications, the issue of urban heat islands and in particular the importance of heat protection were consistently presented together with the more tree-related topics of the Urban ReLeaf project. By combining these topics, the campaign emphasized the role of trees not only as elements of urban greening but also as crucial instruments of climate adaptation and public health protection. This integrated approach underlines that the Urban Trees Campaign is not an isolated or stand-alone initiative, but is firmly embedded within Mannheim's broader strategic framework and complements the city's ongoing activities in climate protection, urban resilience, and citizen engagement.

1.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

The Mannheim tree registry covers the entire city area, with data gaps varying by district but occurring across the city as a whole. Expanding and supplementing the data is therefore beneficial for the entire urban area. For this reason, the Urban Trees Campaign was carried out citywide. Nevertheless, focus areas were selected based on the target audiences that received special attention during the campaign.

While the campaign aimed for broad, citywide participation, concentrating efforts in a specific neighbourhood allowed for more focused data collection, greater visibility of campaign activities, and the opportunity to test strategies for engaging residents in areas where tree data was incomplete. Within the campaign a special focus was put on the district Feudenheim as it is known for its active civic society and residents who are eager to take part in community-driven initiatives. The district also provided good conditions for piloting neighbourhood-focused outreach methods such as a guided walk - an approach that could later be adapted for other areas of the city.

Based on the urban climate analysis, there is also a special focus on the districts that are particularly affected by heat stress. These are primarily the city centre and some adjacent districts. In addition to high heat stress, these areas of the city are also characterized by a high degree of sealing and a relatively low level of urban greenery, which is why selecting them as focus areas appears expedient for various reasons. Moreover, personal impact and vulnerability may also lead to an increased willingness to participate by people living in those areas. For this reason, in autumn 2025, two further activities will be carried out in the city centre and in another heat-affected neighbourhood, in cooperation with local schools. These initiatives are intended to provide children and young people with opportunities for direct participation, while fostering awareness and understanding of the importance of urban greening as a key instrument of climate change adaptation. As this group is personally affected

by the impacts of heat, it can be assumed that their interest and engagement with the topic will be particularly strong.

Figure 5. Screenshots – Urban ReLeaf - Mannheim's Trees app.

The campaign's primary technology was the Urban ReLeaf – Mannheim's Trees mobile app (Figure 5), available in both public and expert versions. The expert version was not used in the public campaign, but is intended for internal use and refinement. The public app is free to download for Android and iOS and enables participants to record tree attributes including location, species, height, stem circumference, and photographs, as well as to update existing records with new or corrected data. It is designed to be user-friendly and intuitive, allowing it to be downloaded and used at any time, and after registration, participants can start using it immediately without prior knowledge or training. However, it is recognized that the use of technical devices and, in particular, unfamiliar apps can pose a barrier to participation and data collection, sometimes limiting access for vulnerable groups. For this reason, specific measures were taken to lower these hurdles and facilitate broader inclusion. To ensure accessibility and usability, the campaign offered simple instructions and live demonstration sessions at public events and during the neighbourhood walk, while on-site assistance was provided for participants with limited technical skills or no prior experience in citizen science activities.

Alongside the app, digital communication channels such as social media platforms and official municipal newsletters were used to promote events, provide user guidance, and share progress updates with the community.

By combining a targeted geographic approach with an intuitive mobile platform, the campaign created opportunities for citizens to contribute valuable environmental data while fostering a sense of local ownership and pride in Mannheim's green infrastructure.

1.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

Citizen participation formed the heart of the Mannheim Urban Trees Campaign. Residents were invited to take an active role in expanding and updating the city's tree database by using the Urban ReLeaf – Mannheim's Trees mobile app. Through this platform, participants can record detailed information about trees in their surroundings, including species, location, height, and trunk circumference, as well as upload photographs. While having a measuring tape on hand can be helpful for accurately recording stem circumference, it is not strictly necessary, and no additional tools beyond a smartphone or tablet with the app are required to participate.

Through the Urban ReLeaf app, interested citizens are given the flexibility to contribute in different ways to the mapping and documentation of Mannheim's trees. Users may either

record entirely new trees by providing their basic attributes or enrich existing entries with additional information. Importantly, it is not necessary for all data fields to be completed in order to make a meaningful contribution. For example, participants may simply upload photographs of trees without adding further details, or they may choose to just record selected attributes. This open and flexible approach allows users to decide for themselves the form and intensity of their engagement, thereby lowering barriers to participation and encouraging contributions from a wide range of individuals, regardless of their level of expertise or available time.

The app provides a comprehensive view of all trees listed in the municipal tree registry, displaying the available information for each recorded attribute. In cases where specific data are missing - for example, the shape of the planting area - this is clearly indicated within the app. At the same time, the platform also displays all newly collected information contributed by participants, ensuring that both existing and newly added data are integrated and presented together in a single, accessible interface. This approach allows for a transparent overview of the urban tree stock while continuously enriching the dataset through citizen contributions.

The Urban ReLeaf app has been made freely available to the public since its release and can be used by all interested citizens without restriction. It is designed to be intuitive and straightforward, requiring no prior training, additional guidance, or specific expertise in order to operate. Nevertheless, effective outreach and citizen engagement remain crucial to ensuring broad awareness and sustained use. To this end, the app's development and promotion were closely connected with Mannheim's Greening Network, which was established in 2023. This network brings together multipliers in the field of urban greening, many of whom are active citizens with additional expertise in biology or related areas. Members of this group were introduced to the app during its development phase, allowing them to accompany the process from the outset and to provide valuable feedback. At the same time, they were able to draw on their personal and professional networks to promote the app within the community, ensuring strong visibility among those already interested in urban greening.

Beyond this target group, the broader public was also addressed from the very beginning, with the app being presented not only at thematically relevant events but also at general civic occasions, such as the city's New Year's reception, to foster wide-reaching participation. It has become evident that user numbers increased particularly in connection with, and in the aftermath of, public events. This effect was supported by the provision of QR codes, which allowed for the direct download of the app either on-site or to take home, as well as by the opportunity to try out the app during the events themselves (for example, at the New Year's Reception 2025). As expected, one barrier to immediate use was the requirement to create an account, which takes time and, in some cases, deterred individuals who were reluctant to provide their email address. All the more beneficial, therefore, was the possibility for interested participants to see the app in action and test it live, giving them a clear sense of what to expect and lowering the threshold for subsequent engagement.

In 2024, the campaign initially targeted a broad audience in order to raise general awareness of the app, with any geographical focus emerging indirectly through the participants reached. In the second year of the campaign, however, a more targeted approach was adopted: during a tree walk (Figure 6) the focus was placed specifically on the Feudenheim district, where there is active public interest in who has submitted inquiries to the city administration regarding tree issues in their district, introducing a new format designed to engage citizens more directly. The collaborative work with this group resulted in more than 100 updates, demonstrating the effectiveness of focused, participatory engagement.

Figure 6. Tree walk in Feudenheim.

The structure of engagement was ongoing rather than limited to one-off events, allowing participants to contribute tree data throughout the year. This flexibility encouraged repeated participation, particularly among individuals and groups with a strong connection to local environmental initiatives. The orientation of the campaign, along with the variety of events and information channels used, contributed to reaching a diverse audience and encouraging broad participation. Anecdotal observations and feedback from partners indicate that participants came from a wide range of age groups, including school-aged children, working adults, and retirees.

Experience from the 2024 campaign provided valuable insights that guided several notable adjustments in 2025. The app's usability was further refined to ensure an even more intuitive and seamless user experience, lowering barriers to participation and making it easier for users of all backgrounds to contribute. In addition, motivational elements were introduced to encourage repeat contributions and sustained engagement over time. These included gamification features, such as ranking systems and achievement indicators, which allowed participants to track their activity and compare contributions within the community, fostering a sense of friendly competition and ongoing involvement in the project.

Data collected through the campaign is stored on a server hosted by Mannheim's Greening Department and is continuously available for access. The data can be viewed at any time in the app by all municipal departments and local policymakers, and can be used to inform tree maintenance, monitor the condition of the urban tree stock, and identify potential locations for future planting.

Over the two years of implementation, the campaign adapted to lessons learned. In 2025, outreach became more geographically focused to address gaps in specific neighbourhoods, and improvements to the mobile app made data entry more intuitive and engaging. These adjustments helped sustain momentum and deepen citizen involvement in building Mannheim's shared green infrastructure.

1.5 Findings and Reflections

The Urban Trees Campaign in Mannheim successfully raised visibility of urban heat and climate adaptation, while actively engaging diverse groups of citizens. Participation ranged from schoolchildren to retirees, with more than 180 users registered in the app and notable peaks in downloads and contributions following public events, supported by simple tools like QR codes and live demonstrations. More detailed figures on the contributions can be found in

Table 1. Not all individuals who took part in campaign activities or expressed interest in the project ultimately downloaded the app; however, this can still be regarded as a positive outcome, as both the project and the app provided many residents with a new entry point to the topic of urban greening and its crucial role in mitigating heat.

Regarding the data maintained in the Tree Registry platform, some clarifications are necessary. The platform was initially populated with data provided by the Mannheim Greening Department, representing City-owned Trees. For these trees, citizens cannot change the official field values; instead, their role is to contribute community suggestions for these values. Conversely, when a citizen adds a new tree, it creates a Community-added Tree. On this second type of tree, citizens can update the values they originally provided. In both cases (City-owned and Community-added trees), citizens can upload Photos. Tables 1, 2, and 3 provide detailed statistics on contributions across these different data types and citizen-submitted values.

Table 1. Number of citizen contributions via the tree app.

Total Citizen Registrations	183
Total Community Trees	104
Total tree pictures uploaded	190
Pictures uploaded during tree creation	147
Pictures added to existing trees	43
Number of Tree Field Values added to trees	586
Number of suggested Community Updated Values added to trees	131

One of the key findings of the campaign relates to the structure and completeness of the tree database itself. Data gaps in the registry are not concentrated in specific districts; rather, they are distributed across the city. The issue is therefore less about missing entire groups of trees and more about the quality and completeness of existing entries. In some cases, trees remain listed even though they may have been removed in the meantime, while in many others important attributes are simply absent. The campaign has therefore highlighted that the main need lies in enriching the existing dataset with additional information rather than filling geographically defined gaps. Table 2 lists all values that have been completely newly recorded and have not yet been displayed in the app.

Table 3 contains the figures from suggestions for parameters that have already been recorded.

Experience has also shown that it is highly beneficial to consider the technical integration of collected data early in the planning process, ensuring that the information is seamlessly accessible and usable for municipal departments.

Table 2. Actual Tree Field Values added to trees.

Tree Field Values	Total (586)
Number of "Tree Height" values added	102
Number of "Stem Circumference" values added	101
Number of "Shape of Planting Area" values added	100
Number of "Crown Diameter" values added	100
Number of "Diagonal/Diameter of Planting Area" values added	97
Number of "Planting area in m ² " values added	86

Table 3. Suggested Community Updated Values added to trees.

Community Updates (Suggestions)	Total (131)
Number of suggested "Tree Height" values added	24
Number of suggested "Stem Circumference" values added	28
Number of suggested "Shape of Planting Area" values added	27
Number of suggested "Crown Diameter" values added	24
Number of suggested "Diagonal/Diameter of Planting Area" values added	28
Number of suggested "Planting area in m ² " values added	0

The campaign also produced valuable technical insights, leading to corresponding adjustments to the app. It became clear that pure data collection is not, in itself, highly attractive to many users. To address this, motivational features such as gamification elements and the creation of a more visible sense of community were introduced, which proved effective in encouraging ongoing contributions.

Finally, the experience confirmed that the initial strategy of targeting a broad audience was valid and justified in order to establish visibility. At the same time, it also became evident that more targeted approaches, combined with personal support, strengthened both the sense of connection to the project and the actual use of the app. Events such as the Feudenheim workshop in 2025, which resulted in more than 100 updates in a single day, clearly demonstrated the effectiveness of this more focused and participatory engagement.

Overall, the campaign's findings underscore the value of combining broad outreach with targeted, supportive engagement, and highlight the importance of user-friendly tools, motivational features, and knowledge about data gaps. These insights provide important lessons for replicating similar urban greening initiatives in other cities.

1.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

The Urban ReLeaf app will remain accessible at least until the end of the project period, continuing to support the enrichment and maintenance of Mannheim's tree database. Two further targeted activities with schools are planned, offering additional opportunities for direct citizen participation and engagement with urban greening. The integration and connection of the collected data with new sources will be continuously reviewed to ensure it is effectively incorporated into the city's existing data ecosystem.

Based on the experience of the pilot, future campaigns are most effective when they combine broad outreach with targeted, participatory engagement. While general awareness-raising reaches a wide audience, focused workshops, on-site support, and interactive events encourage active contributions and a stronger sense of ownership among participants. It is strongly recommended to collaborate closely with existing actors, networks, and local partners, anchoring campaign activities in established structures, events, and initiatives. This approach not only increases visibility but also leverages local expertise and community connections, enhancing both participation and impact.

Overall, the Mannheim pilot demonstrates a model that can be adapted and replicated in other urban contexts, combining user-friendly tools, participatory engagement, and strong collaboration with local stakeholders to foster sustainable citizen involvement in urban greening and climate adaptation.

2 Greenspace Perceptions Campaign

Mannheim is recognized as one of the hottest cities in Germany. In particular, the densely built-up city centre frequently experiences extreme temperatures during the summer months, which can significantly affect the comfort and usability of public spaces. In July and August 2025, a campaign entitled “Stay Cool in Mannheim’s Public Spaces” was conducted to investigate how public spaces in Mannheim are perceived during hot days and to identify measures that contribute to future-oriented urban design. This campaign represents the second major initiative of its kind in Mannheim, following the Urban Trees Campaign, and builds upon several points previously addressed. While the 2025 campaign has a stronger focus on heat prevention, it naturally intersects with the themes of urban greening and tree planting. These thematic overlaps, which are inseparable in practice, will also be reflected throughout this report.

The main component of the 2025 campaign was a survey, with three dedicated survey days serving as key events within the overall initiative. The aim of the campaign is to inform the development of public spaces that provide protection, comfort, and opportunities for relaxation even under extreme heat conditions. The heat-focused aspects of the campaign were already mentioned in the context of the tree campaign, highlighting the continuity and integration of both initiatives.

Participants in the survey were asked to share their perceptions of five central locations in Mannheim: Alter Meßplatz, Friedrichsplatz, Marktplatz, Paradeplatz, and Schillerplatz. The insights gathered are intended to support strategies that enhance the resilience and livability of Mannheim’s public spaces.

2.1 Context and Objectives

Mannheim has been a pioneer in urban heat management, having developed one of the first municipal [Heat Action Plans](#) in Germany in 2021. Even before that a comprehensive climate adaptation concept had evolved in 2019. This early engagement provides a strong foundation for addressing heat stress in public spaces and serves as a natural starting point for initiatives such as the Urban ReLeaf Green Space Perceptions Campaign. Building on this, the city has implemented measures including an unsealing concept, a greening competition focused on the city centre and financial sponsorship of green facades supported by the Mannheim Climate Protection Agency. In addition, Mannheim’s Smart City GmbH is actively driving the city’s transformation into a Smart City, taking a pioneering role in climate monitoring and data-driven urban management. Furthermore, in 2025, Mannheim is updating its Heat Action Plan (HAP), transitioning to a HAP 2.0. Collectively, these measures create a dense network of stakeholders, data, and ongoing initiatives, providing a robust framework for understanding public perceptions of urban green spaces under extreme heat conditions.

Mannheim’s efforts are embedded within a multi-level policy and strategic framework. At the European level, the focus is on promoting climate resilience in cities, encouraging the integration of green and blue infrastructure, and supporting initiatives that enhance urban liveability under extreme heat, such as the EU Adaptation Strategy, the European Green Deal, and the Urban Agenda for the EU. National strategies guide municipalities in implementing heat mitigation measures, public health interventions, and urban greening, including heatwave early warning systems, the promotion of green roofs and facades, and the creation of open green spaces. At the state level, Baden-Württemberg supports cities with targeted guidance and funding instruments to implement heat-resilient designs, including shading, vegetation, water features, and measures to reduce impermeable surfaces. For example, the KLIMOPASS program provides financial support for municipal climate adaptation initiatives.

This multi-level alignment ensures that local initiatives in Mannheim are supported by broader policy objectives, enabling a coordinated approach to heat adaptation and sustainable urban development.

Recent redesign projects in Mannheim illustrate the city's broader commitment to climate-resilient urban development. The Habichtplatz in Käfertal, for instance, has been transformed from a sealed asphalt surface into a green, accessible neighbourhood square, offering cooling effects, enhanced rainwater infiltration, and improved livability. Similarly, the Swansea Square and the planned redesign of Goetheplatz in front of the National Theatre reflect Mannheim's effort to combine urban renewal with climate adaptation, integrating greenery, shading, and spaces for social interaction. These projects underscore the city's strategic objective of creating public spaces that are both environmentally effective and socially inclusive, aligning closely with the goals of the Urban ReLeaf campaign.

Together, these frameworks provide a supportive environment for Mannheim's Urban ReLeaf Green Space Perceptions Campaign, highlighting the importance of creating public spaces that remain safe, comfortable, and accessible during extreme heat events, while fostering synergies with ongoing urban greening and climate adaptation efforts.

The overarching objective of the campaign was to capture citizens' direct perceptions and lived experiences of public spaces during hot summer days, thereby complementing existing climate analyses and adaptation strategies with insights grounded in everyday realities. In doing so, the campaign sought to deepen understanding of how public spaces are used and experienced under extreme heat conditions: how different places are perceived, the purposes for which they are frequented, the activities people pursue, and the locations where they choose to spend time. Equally important was the identification of unmet needs and aspirations to guide the creation of more comfortable and climate-resilient urban environments. A key aim was to give affected individuals a voice and actively involve them in a topic that directly shapes their daily lives and may expose them to considerable stress – thus underscoring both the necessity of action and the existing social pressure to respond effectively. Particular attention was devoted to the perspectives of vulnerable groups, with the goal of strengthening protection and support for those most at risk from heat-related impacts.

2.2 Design and Implementation

The campaign “Cool bleiben auf Mannheims Plätzen” (“Stay Cool in Mannheim's Public Spaces”) was designed as a concise yet strategically embedded initiative addressing the challenges of extreme urban heat. While heat has been a recurring theme in Mannheim's public communication, often framed around awareness-raising and prevention, this campaign added a new dimension by focusing explicitly on the quality, usability, and inclusivity of public spaces under heat stress.

Although the campaign itself was concentrated in July and August 2025, the thematic groundwork had been laid much earlier. Heat was introduced as a focus during the promotion of the Urban ReLeaf project and in connection with Mannheim's earlier Urban Trees Campaign. The forthcoming campaign was announced on the city's project website and highlighted at several events, including Mannheim's New Year Reception and the first Greening Forum in July 2025 (Figure 7), a specialist conference on building greening and biodiverse outdoor design. This long thematic lead-in ensured visibility and contextualization, while the citizen engagement and data collection activities during the summer months formed the campaign's core. Importantly, the surveys themselves were not pre-announced for specific dates or locations, so as to avoid attracting particular groups and instead capture spontaneous, authentic feedback from those who were already using the squares.

Figure 7. Greening forum 2025.

The design and delivery of the campaign were supported by several stakeholders. The Freundeskreis BUGA (Bundesgartenschau - Federal Garden Show) played a central role as a key partner. As an association that had previously managed visitor services during the Federal Garden Show in Mannheim in 2023, its members were highly experienced in direct citizen interaction and deeply interested in issues such as urban greening, fresh air corridors, and the transformation of sealed surfaces into green infrastructure. They were therefore ideally suited to conduct the surveys, contributing several volunteers across the three survey days (Figure 8). The City Media Centre (Stadtmedienzentrum) further supported the campaign by assisting with technical implementation and providing devices for on-site data collection. These contributions ensured that the campaign was both operationally effective and closely connected to Mannheim's broader civic and environmental engagement networks.

The communication strategy was deliberately twofold. On the one hand, the theme of heat and heat protection was widely promoted in advance through public channels, events, and the city's website to raise awareness of climate resilience. On the other hand, the surveys themselves were conducted without public announcement to ensure that feedback reflected the genuine, immediate perceptions of citizens using the spaces under actual heat conditions. This approach allowed the campaign to access spontaneous impressions while maintaining credibility in its data collection. Special emphasis was placed on including a broad range of participants, with attention to vulnerable groups (including homeless individuals, elderly citizens, and individuals with physical disabilities) who are disproportionately affected by extreme heat.

The campaign built upon experiences from Mannheim's previous Urban Trees Campaign (2024 and 2025), which had already introduced the theme of heat adaptation in public communication. The 2025 campaign, however, sharpened the focus on heat stress and public space usability, representing a natural progression in Mannheim's engagement with climate resilience. No major structural changes occurred during the campaign itself, though the integration of technical partners and the adaptation of survey methods to include both digital and paper-based participation reflected a pragmatic response to observed challenges in connectivity, accessibility, and user-friendliness.

Figure 8. Freundeskreis BUGA on the three survey days.

2.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

The campaign was primarily implemented in Mannheim's inner-city districts, focusing on the so-called Quadrate (city centre), as well as selected locations in the Oststadt and Neckarstadt-West. These areas were deliberately chosen due to their intense exposure to summer heat (mainly due to dense building structures, generally high degrees of sealing, and lack of air circulation), high population density, and their diverse urban functions. They represent places where many residents and visitors spend time for work, education, shopping, and daily errands, thus providing an ideal setting for understanding how heat stress affects the quality of life in public space. The chosen squares also differed markedly in their design and amenities – ranging from variations in shading, greenery, and water features to the presence of seating, play equipment, and other forms of urban furniture – allowing for a broad comparative perspective on the usability and resilience of public spaces under extreme heat conditions.

To capture citizen perspectives, surveys were conducted on several central squares: Alter Meßplatz, Marktplatz, Paradeplatz, Schillerplatz and Friedrichsplatz. These sites were not only representative of Mannheim's most frequented public spaces but also provided insight into different modes of use and levels of comfort during hot days. By covering a spectrum of spatial typologies, the campaign ensured a nuanced understanding of heat-related challenges and potential interventions.

The primary technology used for the survey was Partimap (Figure 9), which is a digital participation and mapping tool frequently used in research projects, urban development processes, and citizen science campaigns. At its core, it is an online questionnaire with an interactive map. Therefore, beyond answering structured questions (Appendix A), participants were able to mark their personal location directly on an interactive map. Access to the questionnaire was provided via a link, prominently displayed on information cards (Figure 10) distributed during the campaign. By scanning the QR code on these cards, respondents could complete the survey with any internet-enabled device.

Keep cool in Mannheim's squares

Mannheim is one of the hottest cities in Germany. Especially in the densely built-up city center, temperatures are often extremely high in summer, which can significantly impair the quality of life in public spaces. The *Urban ReLeaf* project investigates how public spaces in Mannheim are perceived on hot days and what measures can contribute to sustainable design. The goal is to create places that offer protection, a pleasant atmosphere, and relaxation even in extreme heat.

This survey allows you to give your personal opinion exclusively on the following five locations in Mannheim: **Alter Messplatz**, **Friedrichsplatz**, **Marktplatz**, **Paradeplatz**, **Schillerplatz**.

In cooperation with the City of Mannheim.

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Figure 9. First survey page on Partimap.

Figure 10. Information cards with QR code leading to the survey.

During the three on-site survey days, the field team engaged citizens directly at the selected squares, using city-provided tablets as well as their own smartphones and tablets. To maximize inclusivity, paper questionnaires were also offered, recognizing that not all

participants were familiar with digital devices or willing to use their own mobile data, and that the public Wi-Fi network in Mannheim, though available, did not provide reliable coverage or sufficient speed at all locations. This multi-modal approach – ranging from mobile and tablet-based input to paper-based participation – ensured broad accessibility while accommodating varying technical skills and user preferences (Figure 11). Each method presented distinct advantages and limitations in terms of connectivity, usability, data transfer, and convenience, underlining the value of combining them. In addition, the survey link, available in both English and German, was published on Mannheim’s Urban ReLeaf project webpage during the campaign period, enabling participation independently of the on-site survey team and further extending the reach of the citizen science initiative.

Figure 11. Survey on Paradeplatz.

Complementing the citizen surveys, environmental monitoring technologies were deployed to contextualize perceptions with objective data. The Smart City Mannheim GmbH provided globe thermometers, which were installed at the selected squares prior to the first survey day and remained in place for several weeks (Figure 12). These instruments measured parameters related to perceived heat stress and allowed a more precise assessment of microclimatic conditions in the urban fabric.

Figure 12. Globe thermometers and TRH sensors.

Additionally, a small number of wearable temperature and relative humidity (TRH) sensors, provided internally by the Urban ReLeaf project, were deployed as supplementary devices during the survey days (Figure 12). These sensors measured temperature and relative humidity and allowed participants to provide subjective feedback on thermal comfort or discomfort. The devices need to be connected to an accompanying app, which requires prior

registration and a basic understanding of the technical setup. Due to this level of complexity and the necessary introduction, the sensors were used only to a limited extent. The field team carried some of the sensors during the surveys to collect additional environmental data and to test their performance in real conditions. While not an integral part of the campaign methodology, these devices served to complement the main data collection efforts.

Together, the combination of citizen engagement tools and environmental sensing technologies created a comprehensive framework that linked subjective experiences with objective measurements. This approach not only advanced the campaign's insights but also contributed to Mannheim's broader efforts as a pilot city within the EU Urban ReLeaf project, fostering citizen science practices and strengthening the city's role as a pioneer in smart, climate-responsive urban development.

2.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

Citizen participation formed the core of the campaign design, ensuring that lived experiences and personal perceptions of heat in public spaces were systematically captured. Engagement was structured as a concentrated activity during July and August 2025, aligning with the summer period when heat stress is most relevant. While broader awareness-raising on heat prevention in Mannheim is ongoing, the campaign focused on a short but intensive window of citizen science and data collection.

To maximize inclusiveness, a dedicated survey team carried out interviews directly on-site across three selected days. This direct approach was particularly effective in reaching participants who might otherwise have been excluded, such as older residents or less digitally literate groups. Citizens were not only respondents but also directly involved as volunteer surveyors, further strengthening local ownership of the process. The survey team consisted of volunteers from the Mannheim-based association Freundeskreis BUGA. The members of this association took on visitor coordination during the Federal Garden Show in 2023 and are therefore used to interacting with other people. In addition, there are thematic connections and a fundamental interest among the volunteers in greening issues. This group was therefore very well suited as a survey team. In total, 23 members participated. They operated in pairs on each site, with some volunteers supporting data collection on multiple days. In preparation, volunteers participated in a training session several days prior to the survey, during which the project and its objectives were presented, relevant knowledge shared, and the questionnaire reviewed in detail. This ensured that all surveyors were well-briefed, familiar with the questions, comfortable with the survey link and technical devices, and able to decide whether to use their personal device or a provided tablet, thereby supporting a smooth implementation on the survey days.

Data collection combined perceptual, spatial, and environmental dimensions. The main instrument was a digital questionnaire delivered via Partimap. The surveys were conducted on three days – 23 July, 2 August, and 10 August 2025 – specifically on different days of the week (Wednesday, Saturday, Sunday) between 12:00 and 14:00 in order to capture a variety of users – from workers on their lunch break to families and leisure visitors – while also taking into account times of increased heat exposure. Approximately 280 questionnaires were completed, with around 235 submitted digitally and about 45 collected on paper for participants less comfortable with mobile devices or where Wi-Fi access was insufficient. A more detailed breakdown can be found in Table 4 and Table 5. While paper questionnaires helped broaden participation, they posed challenges in terms of data quality (e.g. missing timestamps, incomplete answers), underscoring the advantages of digital platforms with built-in validation features.

Table 4. Filled out questionnaires on the three survey days.

	Partimap (235)	Paper (45)	Total (280)
23. Jul	79	10	89
Alter Meßplatz	13	3	16
Friedrichsplatz	10	7	17
Marktplatz	18	0	18
Paradeplatz	20	0	20
Schillerplatz	18	0	18
02. Aug	95	7	102
Alter Meßplatz	16	0	16
Friedrichsplatz	15	7	22
Marktplatz	12	0	12
Paradeplatz	36	0	36
Schillerplatz	16	0	16
10. Aug	52	28	80
Alter Meßplatz	9	8	17
Friedrichsplatz	0	14	14
Marktplatz	12	0	12
Paradeplatz	12	6	18
Schillerplatz	19	0	19
<i>other days</i>	9	0	9

Framework conditions during the survey period were moderate, with no major summer heat occurring at the time. While heat waves did occur in Mannheim during 2025, they unfortunately did not coincide with the survey days. Due to the inclusion of volunteers and the necessary approval processes for conducting surveys in public spaces, it was not possible to collect data during actual extreme heat events. Nevertheless, the survey was deliberately scheduled in July and August to maximize the likelihood of relevant conditions. Some survey days also presented unique situational challenges, such as the Anime Convention attracting a very large crowd at Friedrichsplatz or the Saturday market at Marktplatz, which required flexibility and adaptation by the survey team.

Table 5. Filled out questionnaires on each site.

	Total (280)
Alter Meßplatz	51
Friedrichsplatz	54
Marktplatz	44
Paradeplatz	76
Schillerplatz	55

In addition, project-internal TRH sensors (measuring temperature and relative humidity) were piloted as supplementary tools. These were used by some surveyors during the campaign days, offering indicative climate data and allowing respondents to provide information on thermal comfort or discomfort. As the sensors required connection to a dedicated app and

prior registration, their use was limited to small-scale testing, but they offered valuable insights into the potential for integrating environmental sensing into future campaigns.

Altogether, this mixed-method approach generated a robust dataset that combines subjective perceptions with objective measurements, enabling a multi-layered understanding of heat experiences in public spaces. Although extreme heat events did not occur during the survey days, the data nonetheless provide relevant insights into how citizens interact with and perceive urban spaces in the summer months.

At present, results have not yet been published, as analysis is still underway. Preliminary findings are already being integrated into Mannheim’s Heat Action Plan 2.0 process. The full dataset and detailed analysis will be shared with relevant departments, including planning department, greening department, Smart City GmbH, and the Local Green Deal team, at a later stage as planned. Once analysis is finalized, the data will also be disseminated publicly in appropriate formats, ensuring transparency and feedback to participating communities.

2.5 Findings and Reflections

At this stage, no in-depth analysis has yet been completed, as the process of consolidating data sources and deriving final results is still ongoing. Nevertheless, preliminary findings can already be highlighted, and valuable insights drawn from the campaign.

Citizens clearly indicated that trees (53%) and shading (44%) are the most valued features for comfort on hot days (Figure 13), while approximately 25% reported excessive sun exposure and more than one-third of respondents experienced uncomfortably (25%) or dangerously (10%) high indoor temperatures in their homes, highlighting significant heat vulnerability. These findings underscore the critical importance of climate-adapted public space design. While in-depth analysis is still underway, the survey results and collected information are expected to provide further insights that can inform and improve climate-resilient urban planning, including potential measures such as additional greening, shading, or surface modifications.

Figure 13. Percentage of selected answers to the question: What are the most important criteria for a good stay at this campsite on hot days? (multiple answers possible (up to three)).

An initial compilation of the data recorded by the TRH sensors shows that between June and September 2025, a total of 403 pairs of temperature and relative humidity observations were recorded within 50 km of the Mannheim centre (Figure 14). Cross-referencing this data with measurements from the globe thermometers in the process of an in-depth evaluation appears to be beneficial and interesting.

Figure 14. All Temperature observations.

Beyond data collection, the campaign succeeded in raising the visibility of heat-related issues within the city and fostering public awareness. Volunteer surveyors reported positive interactions and engaging conversations, including with individuals who may not have otherwise participated, generating a sense of community and shared responsibility for urban heat adaptation. Many volunteers expressed enthusiasm for future campaigns, suggesting that the initiative can produce sustained engagement rather than a one-off effect.

Reflections on the campaign reveal several lessons learned. The direct, on-site survey approach worked very well in ensuring high participation and capturing real-time perceptions, particularly for vulnerable groups. The main challenges concerned the technical and practical aspects of data collection: digital tools sometimes faced connectivity issues, and paper questionnaires, while necessary for inclusivity, carried risks of incomplete responses or missing timestamps. These experiences underscore the importance of mixed-method approaches and careful planning for accessibility and usability.

Finally, while the campaign successfully highlighted citizen needs and perceptions, it also reinforced the insight that research and engagement alone do not produce tangible urban

improvements. Concrete interventions, such as the recent Habichtplatz transformation, are essential to deliver visible, experiential benefits for residents. Citizen science efforts thus provide both a foundation for evidence-based planning and a channel to embed public perspectives into the design and implementation of climate-resilient urban spaces.

2.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

The next steps following the Urban ReLeaf pilot in Mannheim will focus on consolidating and analysing the collected data, integrating preliminary insights into the ongoing development of Heat Action Plan 2.0. The findings will inform future urban greening, shading, and heat adaptation measures, helping to create more climate-resilient public spaces. Public dissemination of results is planned to ensure transparency and feedback to participating communities.

For future campaigns, direct on-site engagement by trained volunteers proved particularly effective in reaching diverse and vulnerable groups and should remain central to citizen science approaches. A mixed-method design – combining digital and paper questionnaires with environmental sensors – supports inclusivity while generating both qualitative and quantitative data. Planning surveys around periods of extreme heat, when feasible, could enhance relevance, and structured volunteer training can strengthen outreach and long-term community involvement. Communicating clearly how citizen contributions translate into tangible improvements in public spaces reinforces participation and helps ensure that campaigns have lasting impact.

Overall, the Urban ReLeaf pilot demonstrates that combining citizen engagement, environmental monitoring, and spatial analysis can produce valuable insights for climate-resilient urban planning. The lessons learned provide a foundation for scaling or replicating similar approaches in other contexts, while highlighting the importance of aligning research, policy, and practical implementation to achieve meaningful and lasting benefits for residents.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Survey on Partimap – English version

Keep cool in Mannheim's squares

Mannheim is one of the hottest cities in Germany. Especially in the densely built-up city center, temperatures are often extremely high in summer, which can significantly impair the quality of life in public spaces. The *Urban ReLeaf* project investigates how public spaces in Mannheim are perceived on hot days and what measures can contribute to sustainable design. The goal is to create places that offer protection, a pleasant atmosphere, and relaxation even in extreme heat.

This survey allows you to give your personal opinion exclusively on the following five locations in Mannheim: **Alter Messplatz** , **Friedrichsplatz** , **Marktplatz** , **Paradeplatz** , **Schillerplatz** .

In cooperation with the City of Mannheim.

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I acknowledge that I have read and understand **the Terms of Use and the Privacy Policy.**

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Mannheim's places on hot days

In light of increasing summer heat, the design of public spaces is crucial for well-being in Mannheim. Your feedback reveals which places are perceived as pleasant and shady on hot days and where improvements are needed. In this way, you contribute to the development of climate-resilient and attractive urban spaces.

* Which public place are you currently in?

- Old measuring station
- Friedrichsplatz
- Marketplace
- Paradeplatz
- Schillerplatz

* Why are you in this place? (multiple answers possible (up to three))

- cooling
- relaxation
- Go for a stroll
- dog walking
- to do sports
- Playing/Skating
- On the way to/from another activity
- To meet someone
- Being among people
- Use of the drinking fountain
- Miscellaneous

How do you currently perceive the temperature at this specific location?

- Cold
- Cool
- A bit cool
- Neutral
- Slightly warm
- Warm
- Hot

How do you currently perceive the amount of sunlight at this specific location?

- Far too shady
- Too shady
- Neutral
- Too sunny
- Far too sunny

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*** Where do you like to spend your time on this square on a hot day? (multiple answers possible (up to three))**

- By the water/fountain
- Under the trees
- Under the arcades
- On the green space
- At the playground/skate park
- On the (sunny) open area
- On a sunny bench
- On a shady bench
- In the shadow
- Miscellaneous

*** What are the most important criteria for a good stay at this campsite on hot days? (multiple answers possible (up to three))**

- Drinking fountain
- Water (e.g. a well)
- Toilets
- Play equipment or play/skate area
- benches
- green spaces
- Trees
- Shading
- Floor covering (paving stones, gravel, sand, etc.)
- Miscellaneous

Have you ever used a drinking fountain in Mannheim – for example, in the following squares: Alter Messplatz, Friedrichsplatz, Paradeplatz or Marktplatz?

- Yes
- No
- Not specified

What changes would improve your stay at this campsite on hot days? (Let us know!)

Almost there!

Providing some personal information will help us to better understand and evaluate the survey results.

Photo: Daniel Lukac | © Stadtmarketing Mannheim GmbH

Old

- Under 16
- 16-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65-74
- 75+
- Not specified

Gender

- Female
- Masculine
- Various
- Not specified

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Highest educational qualification

- No school leaving certificate (only primary school)
- Secondary school leaving certificate
- Intermediate school leaving certificate, advanced technical college entrance qualification
- University entrance qualification
- university degree
- Not specified

When you think about where you live, how well protected are you in your house from high temperatures or heat waves during the summer months?

- Very good - my house stays cool even on hot days
- Fairly good - it gets warm, but it's bearable.
- Not good - during heat waves it gets uncomfortably hot in my apartment
- Not at all - my apartment gets dangerously hot during heat waves.
- Not sure
- Not specified

How much time does it take you to walk from your home to this place?

- Less than five minutes
- Five minutes or more
- Not specified

Is this the first time you have answered this survey for this public space?

- Yes
- No

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